

STUDIES IN THE REARRANGEMENT OF CAMPHORQUINONE. PART I. FORMATION AND REACTIONS OF THE INACTIVE MODIFICATION OF 2:2:3-TRIMETHYLCYCLOHEXAN-4-ONE-1-CARBOXYLIC ACID

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Following the work of Samuel and Manasse (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 3157; 1902, 35, 3831), synthetic camphor has been converted into the racemic modification of 2:2:3-trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic acid. The keto-acid on Clemmensen reduction furnishes 1:2:2-trimethylcyclohexane-3-carboxylic acid. The methyl ester of the latter on dehydrogenation with selenium affords *o*-xylene and 1:2-dimethylbenzene-3-carboxylic acid, which is in accord with Simonsen's formula (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 77) for the keto acid. A partial synthesis of the keto-acid is also described.

In the course of their classical researches on the action of sulphuric acid on camphorquinone, Manasse and Samuel (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 3157; 1902, 35, 3831) isolated a dextro-rotatory acid, $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$, m.p. 97-98°, which was believed to be a γ - or a δ -ketonic acid. On oxidation with nitric acid (Gibson and Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1295), however, the keto-acid yielded β -methylpentane- $\beta\gamma$ -tricarboxylic acid (I) in an excellent yield. It followed, therefore, that the keto-acid could be best represented by the two alternative structures (II) and (III).

Subsequently, it was found by Bhagvat and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 77; cf. Bredt-Savelsberg, Zaubrecher and Knieke, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 1801) that the keto-ester on bromination yielded two stereoisomeric dibromo-esters, $C_{11}H_{16}O_2Br_2$, which on treatment with alkali gave a diketone-acid, $C_{10}H_{14}O_4$. This suggested that the dibromo-ester had two bromine atoms attached to the same carbon atom—a fact most simply explained if the original keto-acid had formula (II). In conformity with this view there is the fact that the diketone-acid behaves like an 1:2-diketone and on treatment with alkali passes into a hydroxy dibasic acid, $C_{10}H_{14}O_5$. The latter on dehydration, followed by oxidation, gave successively γ -acetyl- $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylpropane- $\alpha\beta$ -di-carboxylic acid (IV) and α -dimethyl tricarballic acid (V).

The foregoing results appear to establish definitely that the keto-acid, first described by Manasse and Samuel, must be *d*-2:2:3-trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic acid (II). Unfortunately, no direct proof is available regarding the presence of a keto-methylene group in it. (cf. Bhagvat and Simonsen, *loc. cit.*, p. 81).

The formation of a keto-acid (II) from camphorquinone is somewhat remarkable. According to Ingold (*Chem. Soc., Ann. Report, 1927, 122*) a change related to the Wagner rearrangement takes place through the intervention of a molecule of water whereby one of the cyclopentane rings of camphorquinone undergoes fission and the other simultaneously enlarged. This facile rearrangement, which takes place even when camphorquinone is brominated (Manasse and Samuel, *loc. cit.* Evans, Simonsen, and Bhagvat, *J. Chem. Soc., 1934, 444*), possesses more than an ordinary interest and it seemed desirable to undertake the synthesis of the keto-acid in order to establish its constitution definitely.

As has been stated by Gibson and Simonsen (*loc. cit.*) it is a matter of some difficulty to obtain an optically pure specimen of the keto-acid since the latter possesses two centres of asymmetry one of which is expected to suffer racemisation more readily than the other. It was necessary, therefore, to prepare the hitherto unknown racemic modification of the keto-acid, which would serve as a reference compound for purposes of direct comparison.

In the first instance synthetic camphor has been converted into the corresponding quinone by oxidation with selenium dioxide (Simonsen, Evans and Ridgion, *J. Chem. Soc., 1934, 137*). The latter on treatment with cold concentrated sulphuric acid according to the method of Manasse and Samuel (*loc. cit.*) gives the racemic modification of the keto-acid, $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$, m.p. 109°, which has been further characterised by the preparation of a semicarbazone, m.p. 230°. The methyl ester is, however, obtained as an oil, b.p. 100°/4mm., and thus differs from the methyl ester of the corresponding dextro-acid which is a crystalline solid, m.p. 82-83°. The new keto-acid on Clemmensen reduction furnishes a liquid acid, b.p. 118°/5 mm., which readily forms a crystalline *p*-phenylphenacyl ester, m.p. 114°. On the basis of Simonsen's formula for Manasse and Samuel's keto-acid, the above liquid acid should be represented as 1:2:2-trimethylcyclohexane-3-carboxylic acid (VI). As an additional control on the constitution of this acid its methyl ester has been dehydrogenated with selenium at 340° in a closed tube for 28 hours. The resulting product on hydrolysis yields a neutral liquid, which is found to be *o*-xylene by its boiling point and by its oxidation to phthalic acid. The alkaline solution on acidification furnishes an acid which was readily identified as 1:2-dimethylbenzene-3-carboxylic acid (*cf.* Jacobson, *Ber., 1898, 19, 2518*) by its m.p. 144°, and by analysis.

As has been mentioned already, Simonsen and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) were unable to obtain direct evidence regarding the presence of a $-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-$ grouping in the keto-acid (II). It has now been found, however, that the ethyl ester (VII, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) of the keto-acid readily enters into combination with ethyl oxalate leading to the formation of the oxalyl derivative (VII, $\text{R}=\text{CO}'\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) which on distillation under reduced pressure gives up carbon monoxide with the production of ethyl 2:3:3-trimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4:6-dicarboxylate (VII, $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) in an excellent yield.

The latter shows all the properties of a β -keto-acid ester and on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid affords the keto-acid (II). Curiously enough the same product is also obtained when the keto-ester (VII, $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) is heated with moderately concentrated alcoholic potash. This is precisely analogous to the behaviour of ethylcamphor carboxylate (*cf.* Haller and Minguin, *Compt. rend.*, 110, 400; Ruzicka and Kulin, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 748). On digestion with sodium ethoxide in a sealed tube at $150-200^\circ$ for 24 hours, however, the ester (VII, $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) is mainly converted into the triethyl ester (VIII), b.p. $160^\circ/4\text{mm}$. The latter on hydrolysis yields the corresponding tricarboxylic acid as a resin which unfortunately could not be induced to crystallise. The triethyl ester (VIII), however, behaves normally with sodium yielding the keto-ester (VII, $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) which on hydrolysis in the usual way leads to the formation of the keto-acid (II). This constitutes, therefore, a partial synthesis of Manasse and Samuel's keto-acid. The synthesis of the triethyl ester will form the subject of a later communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of dl-Modification of 2:2:3-Trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic Acid

dl-Camphorquinone.—A mixture of *dl*-camphor (30 g.), selenium dioxide (36 g.), and acetic anhydride (30 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath at $140-150^\circ$ for 3 to 4 hours. It was then cooled and filtered, the residue of selenium being washed with acetic acid. The orange-yellow acetic acid solution was partially neutralised with aqueous potassium hydroxide when a curdy yellow precipitate of *dl*-camphorquinone was obtained along with a little unchanged camphor. After one crystallisation from dilute alcohol it was obtained as a yellow powder, m.p. 192° , and was sufficiently pure for the next operation.

Action of cold concentrated sulphuric acid on dl-Camphorquinone: Formation of dl-2:2:3-Trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic Acid (II).—Dry, finely powdered *dl*-camphorquinone (10 g.) was added gradually during half an hour to concentrated sulphuric acid (83 c.c.), cooled in ice and stirred mechanically. The stirring was continued for another 45 minutes when a clear solution was obtained. It was then poured on to crushed ice with stirring. The solution was saturated with salt and extracted repeatedly with ether. The keto-acid was separated from neutral impurities by extracting the ethereal solution with 10% sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline solution was acidified, saturated with salt, and extracted with ether. *dl-2:2:3-Trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic acid* (8 g.) was obtained as a crystalline solid on evaporation of the ether.

The *semicarbazone* was readily obtained on heating a solution of the keto-acid in a little alcohol with aqueous semicarbazide acetate solution. It crystallises from a large volume of spirit as a sandy white powder*, which decomposes at 230° . (Found: C, 54.4; H, 8.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 54.7; H, 7.9 per cent).

* Mixed melting point of this with the semicarbazone of the dextro-acid is 229° .

The pure keto-acid was obtained by warming the semicarbazone with 15% hydrochloric acid till a clear solution was obtained. It was then cooled saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The solid residue obtained on evaporation of the ether was crystallised from water when dl-2 : 2 : 3-trimethylcyclohexane-4-*one*-1-carboxylic acid (II) was obtained in colourless needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 73-74° and containing one molecule of water of crystallisation. (Found : H₂O, 8.9. C₁₀H₁₆O₂ · H₂O requires H₂O, 8.9 per cent).

The hydrated acid readily loses water when kept in a desiccator or heated. The anhydrous acid, thus obtained, crystallises from light petrol in transparent plates melting at 109°. Unlike the corresponding active acid it is not hygroscopic. (Found : C, 65.4; H, 8.7. C₁₀H₁₄O₂ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent).

The methyl ester was prepared by heating the dry keto-acid (2 g.) on a water-bath for 6 hours with absolute methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) and 2 c.c. methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. The alcohol was then distilled off. The residue was taken up in ether and washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water. The ether was evaporated and the liquid remaining distilled in *vacuo*, b.p. 100°/4mm., yield, 2g. Its active isomer is a solid, m.p. 82-83°. (Found : C, 66.4; H, 9.00. C₁₁H₁₈O₂ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.09 per cent).

The ethyl ester (VII, R=H) was prepared by heating the acid (14 g.) on a water-bath for 8 hours with absolute alcohol (80 c.c.) and 8 c.c. of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (saturated at 0°), and working up in a similar manner. It is a liquid boiling at 120°/6 mm., yield 12.5 g. (Found : C, 67.8; H, 9.4. C₁₂H₂₀O₂ requires C, 67.9; H, 9.4 per cent).

Degradation of the Keto-acid, C₁₀H₁₆O₂, to o-Xylene and 1 : 2-Dimethylbenzene-3-carboxylic Acid

1 : 2 : 2-Trimethylcyclohexane-3-carboxylic Acid (VI).—The keto acid (5.1 g.) was heated on a sand bath for 6 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4.5 c.c.) and granulated zinc (60 g.), previously amalgamated with a 5% solution of mercuric chloride. More hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) was then added and the refluxing was continued for 12 hours more. When cold it was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and ether evaporated. The liquid remaining was finally distilled in *vacuo*. It was obtained as a colourless liquid (3.1 g.), boiling at 118°/5 mm. (Found : C, 70.2; H, 10.5. C₁₀H₁₂O₂ requires C, 70.6; H, 10.6 per cent).

The *p*-phenylphenacyl ester crystallises from ethyl alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 114°. (Found : C, 79.1; H, 7.7. C₂₂H₂₈O₂ requires C, 79.1; H, 7.7 per cent).

The methyl ester was prepared by refluxing the above acid (4.9 g.) on the water-bath for 8 hours with absolute methyl alcohol (25 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1.3 c.c.). When cold it was diluted with water and the separated oil taken up in ether. The extract was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water, and the solvent evaporated after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride. The residual oil on distillation gave a colourless liquid boiling at 95°/12 mm., yield, 4.5 g. (Found : C, 71.6; H, 10.8. C₁₁H₂₀O₂ requires C, 71.7; H, 10.8 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of Methyl 1 : 2 : 2-Trimethylcyclohexane-3-carboxylate : Formation of o-Xylene and 1 : 2-Dimethylbenzene-3-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of the methyl ester (4.39 g.) and selenium (7.3 g.) was heated at 340° in a sealed tube for 28 hours. The product was then taken up in ether and filtered. The clear ethereal filtrate was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution (A), and water, and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. It

* Mixed melting point of this acid with the hydrated dextro-acid is 62°.

was carefully fractionated using a short but efficient fractionating column. After the evaporation of the ether the temperature rose up rapidly to 140° and a liquid hydrocarbon (1.5 g.) was obtained boiling constantly at this temperature.

The hydrocarbon, thus obtained, was heated on the water-bath with water (1.75 c.c.), and finely powdered potassium permanganate (9 g.) was added in small amounts, the mixture being well shaken from time to time. After the oxidation was complete, excess of permanganate was decomposed with a few drops of methyl alcohol. It was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated, acidified and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent phthalic acid (1 g.) was obtained. It gave phthalic anhydride on heating, m.p. 131° (mixed m.p. responds to fluorescein test and forms the aniline salt, m.p. 157°).

The sodium carbonate extract (A), on acidification, gave a solid acid (0.6 g.) almost insoluble in cold water. It crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. 144° and was found to be 1 : 2-dimethylbenzene-3-carboxylic acid. (Found : C, 72.2 ; H, 6.8 ; Equiv., 150.9. $C_9H_{10}O_2$ requires 72.0 ; H, 6.7 per cent. Equiv., 150).

A partial Synthesis of the Keto-acid of Manasse and Samuel

Ethyl 2 : 3 : 3-Trimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4 : 6-dicarboxylate (VII, R = CO₂Et).—A mixture of ethyl 2 : 3 : 3-trimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylate (11.5 g.) and diethyl oxalate (7.9 g.) was added very slowly with shaking to a solution of sodium (1.25 g.) in absolute alcohol (16.5 c.c.) cooled in a freezing mixture, and kept overnight. It was then treated with ice-water and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter present. The alkaline solution was acidified with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. The extract was well washed with water, dried and the ether evaporated. The residual oil was heated to 110-120° under reduced pressure for about an hour and then under atmospheric pressure for 3-4 hours till the evolution of carbon monoxide ceased, the temperature during this period being gradually raised from 160° to 200°. It was finally distilled *in vacuo* when the product was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 155°/6 mm., yield 9.9 g. It gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.8 ; H, 8.3. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 63.3 ; H, 8.4 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Trimethylpentane- $\alpha\gamma$ -tricarboxylate (VIII).—The above keto-dicarboxylic ester (5 g.) was heated in a closed tube at 150-200° for 24 hours with a solution of sodium (0.41 g.) in absolute alcohol (24 c.c.). The alcohol was then distilled off under reduced pressure. It was then treated with water and extracted with ether. The residue obtained on evaporation of the ether was fractionated *in vacuo*. At first some low boiling product distilled off and then the temperature rose to 160°/4mm. and about 2.3 g. of *ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -trimethylpentane- $\alpha\gamma$ -tricarboxylate* was obtained. It gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 61.5 ; H, 9.0. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 61.8 ; H, 9.1 per cent).

The free acid was obtained as a gum by hydrolysing the above triethyl ester with aqueous alcoholic potash.

Sodium Condensation of Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Trimethylpentane- $\alpha\gamma$ -tricarboxylate (VIII) : *Formation of Ethyl 2 : 3 : 3-Trimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4 : 6-dicarboxylate* (VII, R = CO₂Et).—The tricarboxylic ester (5 g.), obtained above, was heated on the water-bath with a fine suspension of sodium (0.5 g.) in benzene (12 c.c.). When whole of the sodium went into solution, it was treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil on distillation gave the product (2.5 g.), b.p. 150°/5 mm.

dl-2 : 2 : 3-Trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic Acid (II).—For the hydrolysis of the above keto-ester, concentrated alcoholic potassium hydroxide was found to be better than dilute hydrochloric acid. The keto-ester (2 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours with potassium hydroxide (3 g.) in 20% aqueous alcoholic solution. The alcohol was then evaporated off with the addition of water. The alkaline solution was acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The residue obtained on evaporation of the ether was directly converted into the *semicarbazone*. It crystallised from a large volume of alcohol as a sandy white powder, m.p. 230-31° and there was no depression of the melting point on mixing it with the *semicarbazone* of the keto-acid as obtained directly from camphorquinone. (Found : C, 54.6 ; H, 7.9. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N_2$ requires C, 54.7 ; H, 7.9 per cent).

The *pure* acid was obtained by hydrolysing the *semicarbazone* with dilute hydrochloric acid by warming on the water-bath till a clear solution was obtained. It was then saturated with salt and extracted with ether. On evaporation of the ether a solid residue was obtained which on crystallisation from water melted at 72-73°. On drying in a desiccator it melted at 109°. Moreover, there was no depression of the melting point when the latter was mixed with the *anhydrous* sample of *dl-2 : 2 : 3-trimethylcyclohexan-4-one-1-carboxylic acid*. (Found : C, 65.0 ; H, 8.5. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 65.2 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

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